

Dimensions and Implementation of Development Programmes and Job Performance of Teachers in Private Secondary Schools in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the dimensions and implementations of development programmes in private secondary schools in Delta State. Five research questions guided the study. The study adopted the correlational method of ex-post facto research design. The population of the study comprised 6,512 teachers in private secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The sample size for the study comprised 326 teachers. The sampling techniques that were used for the study are proportionate stratified and convenience sampling techniques. The instrument that was used to collect data in this study is questionnaire. The face and content validities of the questionnaire were determined by the researcher's supervisor and two other lecturers in the Department of Educational Management and Foundations. Cronbach alpha reliability index was used to determine the internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The coefficients include Stages of Development Programmes = 0.80; Training Needs = 0.94; Location of Training = 0.80; and Timing of Training = 0.86. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that the dimensions of development programmes practiced in private secondary schools include stages of development, training needs, location and timing of training. The finding revealed a high level of implementation for each of these dimensions. The study recommended amongst others that private secondary schools should implement a robust system for continuous monitoring and evaluation of development programmes.

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Introduction

The role of teachers in the teaching and learning process is of paramount importance in any school system. Extensive research has consistently demonstrated that teachers play vital roles in influencing students' academic performance and overall educational outcomes (Imhangbe, Victor & Osarenren-Osaghae, 2019). In fact, teachers' input and involvement in terms of their job performance have been identified as the primary and most influential factors that shape and determine students' academic achievements.

The success of a school, particularly in terms of learning engagement and academic performance, is directly linked to the level and quality of teachers' involvement and investment in that particular educational institution. Teachers serve as the facilitators of knowledge, guiding students through the learning process, and imparting essential skills and knowledge to them. Effective teachers possess a deep understanding of their subject matter and pedagogical techniques. They create an engaging and supportive learning environment that encourages active participation, critical thinking, and collaboration among students. Skilled teachers employ various instructional strategies, differentiation techniques, and assessment methods to cater for diverse learning styles and needs within their classrooms.

Furthermore, teachers serve as role models and mentors, inspiring and motivating students to reach their full potential. They provide guidance, support, and individualized attention to help students overcome challenges and excel academically. Teachers also play a crucial role in fostering positive relationships with students, parents, and the broader community, thereby creating a conducive and harmonious learning environment.

It has been observed that the quality of secondary education in Nigeria, as measured by students' performance in examinations conducted by examining bodies as the West African Examinations Council (WAEC), has either progressively declined or fluctuated significantly between very poor performance and fairly acceptable levels. For instance, between 2004 and 2006 students' performance hovered around an overall score average of between 35% and 59.5% in the different subject areas (WAEC, 2008). Whereas their pass rate went as low as 49.98% and 59.22% in 2016 and 2018 examinations respectively (Olowolagba, 2018), the pass rate, however, went as high as 69.54% in 2017 (Ogundare, 2017).

From the WAEC Chief Examiner's report of 2018, it was observed that fewer than 40% of the total number of students that registered and sat for the exams obtained a 5-credit pass including Mathematics and English. In 2020 the report shows that 1,003,668 candidates out of

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1,538,445 students that sat for the 2020 WASSCE examination, representing about 65.24%, obtained at least a credit pass in a minimum of five subjects, that includes English and Mathematics (WAEC, 2020). The 2021 WAEC GCE examiners' report shows that a total of 51,444 candidates wrote the November/December examination out of 52, 973 registered candidates, out of which, only 25,008 candidates representing 48.61 per cent obtained credits and above in a minimum of five (5) subjects, including English Language and Mathematics, of this number, 12, 272 were male candidates, while 12,736 were female candidates. In the same year (2021), the chief examiner's report shows that out of a total of 1,560,261 candidates that sat for the examination, 1,398,370 candidates, representing 89.62 per cent, obtained credit and above in a minimum of any five subjects (with or without English Language and/or mathematics); while 1,274,784 candidates, representing 81.7 per cent, obtained credit and above in a minimum of five subjects, including English Language and mathematics. Although, there seems to be an improvement in the results yearly, much is still expected.

Apart from the WAEC results, the 2021 Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination, UTME, conducted by the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board, JAMB, recorded poor performance by the candidates, as only 168,613 scored above 200 out of the available 400 marks. A perusal of the document issued by the Board after its Policy Meeting in Abuja showed that the performance was a far cry from the 404,740 that scored over 200 out of the 1.9 million that sat for the examination in 2020. In 2020, a total of 2.11 million applicants sought admission into tertiary institutions in Nigeria, with over 300,000 direct entry applicants who needed not to write UTME. In the year 2021, 1,428,208 applied and over 300,000 were also direct entry candidates. The breakdown of the performance of candidates in 2021, as given by JAMB, showed that 168,613 scored 200 marks and above, 64,323 scored 190-199, and 90,688 scored between 180 and 189 marks. Others are 117,970 scoring between 170 and 179 marks, 149,421 scoring between 160 and 169 marks. For the range of 140 to 159 marks, 369,023 candidates fell into that category, while 170,816 scored between 130 and 139 marks.

The above statistics implies that only a small percentage of secondary school graduates meet the requirements for admission to tertiary (higher) education institutions. The recognition of this development among other things apparently informed the review and introduction of newer policies on education aimed at reforming and revitalizing the education system and remedying the falling quality and standard of education especially at the secondary level in the country (Imhangbe, 2017). As teachers play central and critical part in shoring the quality and

standard of education given and received, improvement of teachers and their productivity formed greater part of the reform efforts. One of such policies aimed at improving teachers' job performance is professional development which is exposing them to newer and more effective ways and methods of teaching and learning thereby honing their skills (Osayamen, et al., 2019).

Staff development as viewed by Okunade (2016) is the core human resource management (HRM) function in organisations and it is a process of expanding the knowledge, productivity, programmes that will enhance workers optimal performance. Human resource development is very fundamental in every organization; it has to do with the education, skills levels, and problem-solving abilities that will enable an individual to be a productive worker in the global economy of the 21st century.

Staff development has been accepted as an effective method of increasing the knowledge and skills of teachers in order to enable them teach more effectively. According to Lawal (2014), staff development programmes for teachers are important aspects of education process that deal with the art of acquiring skills in the teaching profession. They are essential practices that enhance subject mastery, teaching methodology and classroom management. The objective of staff development programmes is that it ensures the promotion of professional growth, helps to improve pedagogical skills, keeps teachers abreast with new knowledge, meets particular needs, such as curriculum development and orientation, helps in leadership responsibility, helps new teachers to adjust to teaching field, helps to promote mutual respect among teachers and recognizes the need for modern teaching methods (Madumere-Obike, 2017). These objectives can only be achieved if the dimensions of staff development programme are effectively applied. The dimensions, which this study will focus on include stages of development programme, training needs of teachers, location of training and timing of training.

Staff development programmes for secondary school teachers typically consist of several stages designed to enhance their skills, knowledge, and effectiveness in the classroom. Although the specific stages may vary depending on the programme or institution, the commonly observed stages include assessment and needs analysis; goal setting; planning and design; implementation; and monitoring and evaluation.

The assessment and needs analysis stage involves assessing the current competencies and identifying the professional development needs of teachers through various methods, such

as surveys, observations, or interviews. Based on the needs analysis, specific goals and objectives are established to address the identified areas for improvement. These goals may include enhancing subject knowledge, pedagogical skills, classroom management techniques, or adopting innovative teaching methods. In the planning and design stage, a comprehensive plan is developed to outline the strategies, resources, and activities required to meet the established goals. This may involve selecting appropriate training programmes, workshops, conferences, or other learning opportunities.

The implementation stage involves providing teachers with the necessary training, resources, and support to acquire new knowledge and skills. This can include attending professional development sessions, participating in workshops or seminars, engaging in collaborative learning communities, or undertaking advanced studies. Ongoing monitoring and evaluation of teachers' progress and the effectiveness of the staff development programme is crucial. This can be done through classroom observations, feedback from mentors or supervisors, self-assessment, or the use of assessment tools to measure changes in teaching practices and student outcomes.

By addressing teachers' professional needs and providing targeted training, these programmes can enhance teachers' subject knowledge, pedagogical skills, and instructional practices. This, in turn, can lead to increased teacher confidence, motivation, and job satisfaction, resulting in improved student learning outcomes. Additionally, staff development programmes can promote collaboration and the sharing of best practices among teachers, fostering a culture of continuous improvement within the school community.

The training needs of teachers has the potential of also influencing the performance of secondary school teachers. For instance, the training needs involves conducting a thorough assessment of teachers' current competencies and identifying their professional development needs. This can be achieved through surveys, observations, or interviews to determine areas for improvement such as subject knowledge, pedagogical skills, technology integration, or classroom management techniques. Addressing these training needs through targeted professional development can equip teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to enhance their instructional practices, resulting in improved student outcomes and increased job performance.

The training need also involves setting specific goals and objectives based on the identified professional development needs. This may include developing expertise in a specific

subject area, mastering new teaching methodologies, or acquiring leadership skills. Training programmes that align with these goals can empower teachers to expand their knowledge base and improve their instructional strategies, enabling them to deliver high-quality lessons and engage students effectively. The training needs also involves designing a comprehensive plan to meet the established goals. Teachers may require training in instructional design, curriculum development, or the use of educational technology tools. By providing training in planning and design, teachers can develop well-structured lesson plans, incorporate differentiated instruction, and utilize appropriate instructional resources, leading to more engaging and effective teaching practices.

The training needs also involves providing teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to implement the planned strategies effectively. This may involve training in specific teaching methods, assessment techniques, or the integration of technology in the classroom. Effective training can enhance teachers' instructional practices, enable them to create a positive learning environment, and improve student engagement and achievement.

The training needs also involves building teachers' capacity to monitor and evaluate their own instructional practices. This may include training in data analysis, formative assessment strategies, or reflective practices. Training equips teachers with the skills to assess student progress, identify areas for improvement, and make data-informed instructional decisions. This leads to continuous professional growth and improved job performance. By addressing the training needs, secondary school teachers can enhance their pedagogical skills, subject knowledge, instructional strategies, and assessment practices. This, in turn, can positively influence their job performance by fostering student engagement, promoting higher levels of achievement, and creating a conducive learning environment.

The location of training in staff development programmes for secondary school teachers can vary depending on the specific programme and the resources available. Training sessions can take place within the school premises, at regional education centres, at universities or colleges, or at off-site locations such as conference venues or hotels. Each location has its own advantages and potential impact on the job performance of teachers. For instance, if training sessions are held within the school premises or nearby, it becomes more convenient and accessible for teachers to attend. This reduces the need for travel time and associated costs, making it easier for teachers to participate in the training. When training is easily accessible, teachers are more likely to attend regularly and actively engage in the learning process, which

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can positively impact their job performance. The physical environment where training takes place can have a significant influence on the learning experience and subsequent job performance. A well-designed and comfortable training venue can enhance concentration, engagement, and information retention. A conducive learning environment can promote active participation, collaboration, and the application of new knowledge and skills, thereby positively impacting teachers' performance in the classroom.

Different training locations may offer varying levels of resources and facilities. For instance, universities or education centres may have specialized equipment, libraries, or technology-enhanced classrooms that can enhance the training experience. Access to such resources can enable teachers to explore new teaching methods, engage in hands-on activities, and access research-based information, all of which can positively influence their job performance. Off-site training locations, such as conference venues or hotels, often bring together teachers from different schools and regions. This allows for networking and collaboration opportunities with peers and experts from diverse backgrounds. Interacting with colleagues from other schools and sharing experiences, ideas, and best practices can inspire teachers, broaden their perspectives, and provide them with valuable insights to improve their teaching methods and overall job performance.

Holding training sessions away from the school premises can help create a distraction-free environment, away from the demands and interruptions of daily school routines. This allows teachers to focus solely on their professional development and engage more deeply with the training content. Minimizing distractions can enhance the learning experience and improve the application of new knowledge and skills in the classroom, leading to improved job performance. It is important to note that while the location of training can have an impact on job performance, it is just one factor among many that influence teachers' effectiveness. Other dimensions such as the timing of training should be considered as an important dimension of staff development programmes.

Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) suggests that Continuous Professional Development (CPD), spread out over an extended period, tends to have a more significant impact on teacher practice and student outcomes than one-off workshops or isolated training events. CPD involves ongoing learning opportunities that are integrated into teachers' regular schedules, allowing them to apply new knowledge and skills gradually and reflect on their practice over time. Providing training at the time when teachers need specific knowledge or skills can be

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highly effective. Just-in-time training responds to immediate needs and challenges faced by teachers in their classrooms. For example, if a school is implementing a new instructional approach, providing targeted training and support before its implementation can better equip teachers to integrate it effectively into their teaching practice.

Training can be delivered synchronously (in real-time) or asynchronously (self-paced, online). Both formats have their advantages. Synchronous training allows for immediate interaction, feedback, and collaborative learning among participants. According to Hew and Cheung (2013), asynchronous training, such as online modules or courses, provides flexibility in terms of timing and allows teachers to access training materials at their own convenience. The timing of training delivery should consider teachers' schedules and availability. The timing of training sessions within the school year can also impact job performance. According to Opfer and Pedder (2011), avoiding periods of high workload, such as during major assessments or examinations, can help minimize stress and ensure that teachers can fully engage with the training content. Providing training during school holidays or professional development days can be beneficial, as teachers can focus solely on their professional growth without the pressures of day-to-day teaching responsibilities.

The timing of training is closely linked to the availability of ongoing support and follow-up activities. Yoon et al. (2007) argued that effective staff development programmes include opportunities for teachers to apply newly acquired skills, receive feedback, and engage in reflective practices over an extended period. Follow-up sessions or coaching can help reinforce and deepen teachers' understanding and implementation of new strategies, leading to sustained improvements in job performance.

As shown above, staff development programmes for secondary school teachers involve several stages, including assessment and needs analysis, goal setting, planning and design, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation. These stages address teachers' professional needs, enhance their skills and knowledge, and improve their instructional practices. In view of these, the aim of this study is to examine the dimensions and implementation of development programmes in private secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the dimensions of development programmes in private secondary schools in Delta State?

2. What is the level of implementation of the stages of development programmes among private secondary schools in Delta State?
3. What is the level of implementation of the training needs of teachers among private secondary schools in Delta State?
4. What is the level of implementation of the location of training among private secondary schools in Delta State?
5. What is the level of implementation of the timing of training among private secondary schools in Delta State?

Methods

Design and Population of the Study

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population comprised 6,512 teachers in private secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria.

Participant Selection

A sample of 326 teachers were selected through proportionate stratified and convenience sampling techniques. A proportional stratified sampling technique is a sampling method in which different strata in a population are identified and in which the number of elements drawn from each stratum is proportional to the relative number of elements in each stratum. The reason for this choice of sampling technique was because all the Local Government Areas that were used in the study did not have equal number of students and teachers. In doing this, the researcher estimated the percentage of the sample size in relation to the overall population size, which resulted in 5% for teachers. A convenience sampling technique on the other hand, is a sampling technique in which the researcher requests volunteers from a group of people who meet the general requirements of the study. The researcher in using the sampling technique, decided to use any teacher that were available and agreed to participate in the study, having met the requirement of being a teacher studying at the selected school.

Measures

The instrument that was used to collect data in this study are two sets of questionnaires, titled Questionnaire on Dimensions and Implementation of Development Programmes (QDIDP). The questionnaire contains two sections. Section A contains the demographic data of the teachers such as gender and location of school. Section B contains instrument on items that were used to measure the various dimensions of Development Programmes and their implementation. The

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items were structured on a 4-point scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree. The face and content validities of the questionnaire were determined by experts in the Department of Educational Management and Foundations. They examined the questionnaire in terms of content and suitability of the items to the objective of the study. Their suggestions for improvement were effected to make the instrument to be considered more valid.

In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, the questionnaire was administered to 50 teachers in public secondary schools who were not be part of the main study. The data were analysed using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient to determine its measures of internal consistency. It yielded a coefficient that was used to estimate the reliability coefficient of the instrument. The coefficients include Stages of Development Programmes = 0.80; Training Needs = 0.94; Location of Training = 0.80; and Timing of Training = 0.86.

Data Collection

The questionnaire was administered directly to the respondents by the researcher with the help of three guided research assistants. The researcher and the assistants went to the schools to meet the teachers. She sought and obtained the permission of the principal of the schools. Salient areas of the questionnaire were explained to them by the researcher and assistants to enhance their understanding of the items in the questionnaire. The completed questionnaire was retrieved immediately.

Data Analysis

The data obtained were analysed with mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. A benchmark of 2.50 was used in making decision. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was used for the data analysis.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the dimensions of development programmes in private secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean rating of the dimensions of development programmes in private secondary schools in Delta State

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Stages of Development	2.97	0.24	Agreed
2	Training Needs	2.82	0.37	Agreed

3	Location	3.00	0.26	Agreed
4	Timing of Training	2.76	0.42	Agreed
Average Mean		2.89	0.32	Agreed
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 1 shows the mean rating of the dimensions of development programmes in private secondary schools in Delta State. From the result, the mean score ranged from 2.76 to 3.00 with an average mean of 2.89. The criterion mean used for the assessment is 2.50, which means that all the dimensions were accepted as the dimensions of development programmes in private secondary schools in Delta State. These dimensions include stages of development, training needs, location and timing of training.

Research Question 2: What is the level of implementation of the stages of development programmes among private secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean rating of the level of implementation of the stages of development programmes among private secondary schools in Delta State

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Educating teachers in diverse assessment methods to gauge student progress	3.29	0.72	High
2	Empowering teachers to take on leadership roles within their schools or educational communities.	3.29	0.77	High
3	Adding classroom observations sessions to assist teachers in improving their teaching techniques.	3.29	0.62	High
4	Before starting the development program, it's important to identify the basic skills of teachers.	3.28	0.66	High
5	Training teachers to analyse student data for informed instructional decisions.	3.23	0.75	High
6	Fostering effective communication between teachers and parents to support student learning.	3.22	0.81	High
7	Addressing ethical considerations and professional conduct in the teaching profession.	3.19	0.80	High
8	Equipping teachers with strategies to support students with special needs	3.17	0.83	High

9	Assessing the effectiveness of the development program.	3.10	0.90	High
10	Developing teachers' awareness to cultural diversity in the classroom.	3.02	0.85	High
11	Including reflective activities for teachers to evaluate their teaching.	2.84	0.99	High
12	Addressing the effective use of educational technology tools to enhance teaching and learning experiences.	2.46	1.07	Low
13	Teaching methods to adapt instruction for diverse student learning styles and abilities.	2.21	0.95	Low
14	Encouraging teachers to collaborate with colleagues	1.97	0.88	Low
Average Mean		2.97	0.83	High

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 2 shows the mean rating of the level of implementation of the stages of development programmes among private secondary schools in Delta State. From the result, the mean score ranged from 1.97 to 3.29 with an average mean of 2.97. The criterion mean used for the assessment is 2.50, which means that the level of implementation of the stages of development programmes among private secondary schools in Delta State is high.

Research Question 3: What is the level of implementation of the training needs of teachers among private secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 3: Mean rating of the level of implementation of the training needs of teachers among private secondary schools in Delta State

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Developing skills to effectively use educational technology tools for teaching	3.15	0.92	High
2	Enhancing verbal and nonverbal communication skills to effectively engage with students	3.09	0.82	High
3	Learning to facilitate group work	3.06	0.91	High
4	Enhancing instructional strategies that promote effective learning in the classroom.	3.03	0.89	High
5	Developing awareness of cultural diversity	2.98	0.88	High

6	Learning to interpret and utilize student performance data to inform instructional decisions.	2.98	0.99	High
7	Understanding ethical considerations of professional conduct within the teaching profession.	2.91	1.03	High
8	Equipping teachers with techniques to foster critical thinking skills in students.	2.90	1.07	High
9	Acquiring strategies to address diverse learning needs within a single classroom.	2.82	1.01	High
10	Acquiring coping strategies to manage stress in the demanding teaching environment.	2.79	1.15	High
11	Understanding how to support students with special needs	2.66	1.03	High
12	Developing strategies for effective collaboration with parents.	2.62	1.09	High
13	Training in managing time effectively to balance teaching responsibilities	2.59	1.09	High
14	Learning to design various types of assessments	2.42	1.06	Low
15	Training in creating a conducive learning environment	2.32	1.10	Low
Average Mean		2.82	1.00	high
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 3 shows the mean rating of the level of implementation of the training needs of teachers among private secondary schools in Delta State. From the result, the mean score ranged from 2.32 to 3.15 with an average mean of 2.82. The criterion mean used for the assessment is 2.50, which means that the level of implementation of the training needs of teachers among private secondary schools in Delta State is high.

Research Question 4: What is the level of implementation of the location of training among private secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 4: Mean rating of the level of implementation of the location of training among private secondary schools in Delta State

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Conducting training through live webinars, allowing teachers to participate from their own locations.	3.52	0.74	High

2	Partnering with specialized institutes or organizations that focus on teacher professional development.	3.49	0.66	High
3	Using centres that provide a variety of educational resources, making learning more interactive and engaging.	3.46	0.81	High
4	Organizing training sessions in public libraries, providing a community-based and easily accessible location.	3.40	0.80	High
5	Establishing dedicated centres within educational institutions focused solely on teacher development.	3.39	0.81	High
6	Using private training centres that offer specialized facilities and equipment for professional development.	3.38	0.89	High
7	Offering self-paced online courses that teachers can complete at their own convenience.	3.38	0.81	High
8	Offering training through virtual platforms, enabling teachers to participate remotely from their own locations.	3.28	0.98	High
9	Holding training at recreational facilities that offer a change of environment and a relaxed atmosphere.	3.28	0.88	High
10	Utilizing government facilities for teacher development programmes.	3.23	0.95	High
11	Collaborating with teacher associations to provide training at their events or facilities.	3.14	1.00	High
12	Organizing training workshops at external venues, such as conference centres or training facilities.	2.99	0.85	High
13	Collaborating with nearby educational institutions to provide training services.	2.96	0.78	High
14	Hosting training sessions in venues that offer unique learning experiences and inspiration.	2.94	0.81	High
15	Conducting training sessions within the premises of the school where teachers work, making it convenient and familiar.	2.34	1.15	Low
16	Using facilities designed for corporate training, which may offer modern technology and amenities.	2.05	1.14	Low

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17	Offering training sessions as part of educational conferences, bringing teachers together for learning and networking.	1.90	1.04	Low
18	Holding training programmes at colleges or universities, facilitating access to educational resources.	1.90	1.01	Low
Average Mean		3.00	0.89	high
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 4 shows the mean rating of the level of implementation of the location of training among private secondary schools in Delta State. From the result, the mean score ranged from 1.90 to 3.52 with an average mean of 3.00. The criterion mean used for the assessment is 2.50, which means that the level of implementation of the location of training among private secondary schools in Delta State is high.

Research Question 5: What is the level of implementation of the timing of training among private secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 5: Mean rating of the level of implementation of the timing of training among private secondary schools in Delta State

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Providing self-paced online courses that teachers can complete at their own pace.	3.36	0.85	High
2	Conducting training sessions after regular school hours to accommodate teachers' schedules.	3.34	0.86	High
3	Offering training during extended breaks or vacations when teachers have more availability.	3.15	1.04	High
4	Hosting intensive training programmes during the summer months when schools are closed.	3.11	1.06	High
5	Offering full-day or multi-day workshops during weekends or breaks.	2.99	1.18	High
6	Organizing workshops on weekends to avoid disrupting regular school days.	2.94	1.04	High
7	Designating specific days within the school calendar for professional development activities.	2.81	1.21	High

8	Providing training sessions early in the morning before regular school hours.	2.61	1.18	High
9	Offering training in the evenings to allow teachers to attend after their teaching duties.	2.10	1.19	Low
10	Conducting training on days when students are released early, maximizing teacher participation.	2.03	1.15	Low
11	Organizing sessions on a rotating basis so that all teachers have an opportunity to attend.	1.91	1.14	Low
Average Mean		2.76	1.08	high
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 5 shows the mean rating of the level of implementation of the timing of training among private secondary schools in Delta State. From the result, the mean score ranged from 1.91 to 3.36 with an average mean of 2.76. The criterion mean used for the assessment is 2.50, which means that the level of implementation of the timing of training among private secondary schools in Delta State is high.

Discussion

Dimensions of Development Programmes in Private Secondary Schools in Delta State

The first finding revealed that the dimensions of development programmes practiced in private secondary schools in Delta State include stages of development, training needs, location and timing of training. This finding highlights several key aspects of effective professional development within this context. Private secondary schools in Delta State recognize the importance of implementing development programmes that align with the goals of education. Understanding and addressing the unique training needs of teachers is crucial for the success of development programmes. These needs encompass a wide range of areas, including pedagogical skills, subject knowledge, technology integration, and socio-emotional development. The findings suggest that private secondary schools in Delta State are attentive to identifying these specific needs and designing programmes that cater to them. By conducting thorough assessments of the skills and competencies required at various levels, schools can customize training programmes to enhance the capabilities of teachers and meet the diverse learning needs of students. The geographical location of private secondary schools plays a

significant role in shaping the development programmes. Delta State, with its diverse cultural and social landscape, requires schools to consider local contexts and adapt their programmes accordingly. The findings suggest that schools in the state are mindful of the importance of incorporating regional perspectives into their development initiatives. By contextualizing programmes to the local environment, schools can foster a stronger connection between students and their community, promoting a sense of belonging and relevance in the learning process.

The timing of training sessions is a critical factor in ensuring effective participation and engagement. Private secondary schools in Delta State, as indicated by the findings, recognize the importance of strategic timing for their development programmes. This could involve aligning training sessions with academic calendars, examination periods, or specific milestones in the school year. Strategically timed training sessions allow for maximum participation and minimal disruption to the regular academic schedule. Moreover, they enable educators and students to apply the acquired knowledge and skills immediately, reinforcing the impact of the development programmes.

The above finding aligned with the result of previous studies. For instance, Abimbola and Aina (2018) highlight the importance of tailoring professional development programmes to the needs of teachers at different stages of their careers. Research by Darling-Hammond (2009) echoes this, emphasizing the need for novice teachers to focus on fundamental skills while experienced educators may benefit from leadership development or specialized knowledge acquisition. Egbo (2015) emphasizes the need to consider the stage of development within the school itself. Newer schools might prioritize foundational infrastructure and pedagogical training, while established institutions may focus on advanced curricula or specialized skills for specific faculty roles. Aminu and Adeyemi (2015) argue for incorporating needs assessments into program design, ensuring development activities address specific gaps identified through surveys, observations, and teacher self-evaluations. Nwaokoro and Ogonnaya (2014) emphasize the need for accessible and convenient training locations and schedules to optimize teacher participation and engagement. This can involve decentralizing programmes, offering flexible online options, or scheduling sessions outside regular school hours.

Level of Implementation of the Stages of Development Programmes among Teachers in Private Secondary Schools in Delta State

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The second finding showed that the level of implementation of the stages of development programmes among private secondary schools in Delta State is high. This finding suggests several potential implications. It is indicative of a proactive and effective approach to holistic education. This positive outcome suggests that the high level of implementation reflects a commitment to providing education that goes beyond academics. Private secondary schools often have the flexibility to design their educational programmes based on specific philosophies and values. The high level of implementation suggests that these schools align with educational philosophies that emphasize the importance of addressing different stages of development programme.

The acknowledgement and implementation of stages of development programmes signal an understanding of the diverse needs of teachers at various points in their educational journey. Recognizing that teachers' progress through different developmental stages in their career, schools are tailoring their programmes to provide appropriate content. A high level of implementation suggests that teachers in private secondary schools receive adequate training and professional development to effectively execute their tasks. Teachers who are well-equipped with the knowledge and skills required for implementing such programmes contribute significantly to their success.

The finding agrees with Abimbola and Aina (2018), who highlighted the importance of tailoring professional development programmes to the needs of teachers at different stages of their careers. Research by Darling-Hammond (2009) echoes this, emphasizing the need for novice teachers to focus on fundamental skills while experienced educators may benefit from leadership development or specialized knowledge acquisition. The finding is also in line with Egbo (2015), who emphasized the need to consider the stage of development within the school itself. Newer schools might prioritize foundational infrastructure and pedagogical training, while established institutions may focus on advanced curricula or specialized skills for specific faculty roles.

Level of Implementation of the Training Needs of Teachers among Private Secondary Schools in Delta State

The third finding revealed that the level of implementation of the training needs of teachers among private secondary schools in Delta State is high. This finding signifies a commitment to professional development and a recognition of the crucial role educators play in the overall success of the educational system. The high level of implementation suggests

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that private secondary schools in Delta State place a strong emphasis on the professionalism and continuous development of their teaching staff. Recognizing that well-prepared and informed teachers contribute significantly to student success, schools are actively investing in their professional growth. The finding indicates that schools are not only providing generic training but are customizing programmes to address the specific needs of their teaching staff. This tailored approach ensures that teachers receive training that directly aligns with the challenges and requirements of their respective subjects, grade levels, and teaching methodologies.

The high level of implementation suggests that schools in Delta State are proactive in keeping their teaching staff abreast of the latest educational practices, pedagogical approaches, and technological advancements. This commitment to staying current with educational trends is vital for fostering effective teaching and learning environments. The successful implementation of teacher training programmes often requires substantial investment in resources and infrastructure. Schools with a high level of implementation are likely allocating sufficient funds and technology to support professional development initiatives. This commitment demonstrates the school's dedication to fostering a culture of continuous learning. The finding may also indicate a culture of collaboration and peer learning within schools. Teachers may be encouraged to share best practices, insights, and experiences, fostering a supportive community of educators. Collaborative learning environments contribute to a positive school culture and enhance the overall effectiveness of training initiatives.

The above finding agrees with Aminu and Adeyemi (2015), who argue for incorporating needs assessments into program design, ensuring development activities address specific gaps identified through surveys, observations, and teacher self-evaluations. The finding also aligns with Guskey's (2003) recommendation to prioritize data-driven professional development that directly addresses identified needs. The finding is also in line with Adeola and Akintunde (2012), who stressed the importance of aligning development programmes with desired learning outcomes and student needs. This ensures teachers gain skills directly applicable to improving classroom practice and ultimately benefitting their students.

Level of Implementation of the Location of Training among Private Secondary Schools in Delta State

The fourth finding showed that the level of implementation of the location of training among private secondary schools in Delta State is high. This finding suggests a strategic and

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effective approach to organizing professional development activities. A high level of implementation indicates that schools are mindful of the accessibility and convenience of training locations. Selecting venues that are easily reachable for teachers minimizes disruptions to their daily routines and encourages greater participation. The finding may reflect a nuanced understanding of the geographical context of Delta State. Private secondary schools in the region may be selecting training locations that take into account the diverse landscapes and transportation infrastructure of the area.

Schools with a high level of implementation may leverage their own facilities for training purposes. This approach can contribute to cost-effectiveness and familiarity for teachers, creating a comfortable and conducive environment for professional development. The high level of implementation may indicate that training locations are strategically chosen to integrate with local resources and community assets. This approach aligns with a holistic view of education that extends beyond the school premises, encouraging teachers to connect with and draw inspiration from their surrounding environment. Implementation of training locations may involve a variety of settings, including classrooms, seminar halls, outdoor spaces, or even virtual platforms. This flexibility caters to different learning preferences and enhances the overall training experience for teachers. Schools with a high level of implementation likely align their choice of training locations with their overall educational goals. For example, if a school emphasizes community engagement, training sessions held in local settings may enhance the connection between teachers and the community.

The above finding agrees with Nwaokoro and Ogbonnaya (2014), who emphasized the need for accessible and convenient training locations and schedules to optimize teacher participation and engagement. This can involve decentralizing programmes, offering flexible online options, or scheduling sessions outside regular school hours. It also aligns with Emenyeonu and Ogwuegbu (2013), who point out the value of contextually relevant training experiences that address the specific challenges and resources available within local communities and schools. Tailoring locations and timings can facilitate this context-specific learning.

Level of Implementation of the Timing of Training among Private Secondary Schools in Delta State

The fifth finding revealed that the level of implementation of the timing of training among private secondary schools in Delta State is high. This finding indicates a thoughtful and

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strategic approach to professional development. A high level of implementation suggests that private secondary schools in Delta State carefully plan training sessions to align with academic calendars. Timing training sessions during periods of low academic load, such as school breaks or teacher planning days, helps maximize teacher participation without disrupting regular classroom activities. Private secondary schools with a high level of implementation likely take into account examination periods when scheduling training. Avoiding crucial examination times ensures that teachers can focus on preparing students for assessments, demonstrating an understanding of the academic priorities within the school year.

The timing of training sessions may be strategically spread throughout the academic year. This approach allows teachers to benefit from continuous professional development, preventing information overload and giving them time to apply new knowledge and skills in the classroom gradually. Schools with a high level of implementation may schedule training sessions to coincide with school events or initiatives. For example, timing training around parent-teacher conferences or other collaborative activities can enhance the overall impact of professional development. The high level of implementation may indicate flexibility in the timing of training to accommodate teacher schedules. Offering a range of training sessions at different times of the day or week acknowledges the diverse commitments and responsibilities of educators.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that private secondary schools in Delta State prioritize development programmes with a high level of implementation across various dimensions. This suggests a focus on structured development processes, addressing teacher training needs, and ensuring training logistics like location and timing are well-considered. While the high implementation is promising, it would be beneficial to explore the effectiveness of these programmes in achieving desired outcomes. Future research could investigate the impact of these development programs on teacher satisfaction, skill development, and ultimately, student learning. The following recommended are hereby given:

1. Private secondary schools should implement a robust system for continuous monitoring and evaluation of development programmes.
2. Private schools should continue customizing development programmes to address the specific stages of development, training needs, and preferences of teachers

3. Private schools should design programmes with flexibility to accommodate different learning styles and preferences
4. Private schools should leverage technology for training delivery, especially considering the high level of implementation of technology in the location and timing of training
5. Schools should align the timing of development programmes with the academic calendar to minimize disruptions during critical periods such as examinations.

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